

Brand Management in Product Customization Dimensions Participation in Building and Customer Experience Management.

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Abstract: This article is for synthetic purposes. Brand management conceptual framework for product customization dimensions. Using theoretical synthesis and related research developed into a conceptual framework that consists of various factors, namely Customer Coproducer, Customer Experience management, Collaborative Management and Customization Customization Which leads to the development of brand value There are five main components: brand awareness. Perceived quality brand group Brand image and brand loyalty developing successful brand values Business organizations must consider 3 main factors which are Customer Coproducer, Customer Experience management and collaborative Management Which this research framework has influences to promote and brand value management in product customization dimensions.

Keyword: Customer Coproducer, Customer Experience management, Collaborative Management,

Customization

I. Introduction

The business of producing products to meet the needs of consumers in the digital age resulting from the rapid technology development. Operators must consider marketing strategies that are appropriate for each era. That are different with results from technology or competitors on the same production line Therefore, each era of marketing is different. Caused by continuous product development in the past, it was a production-oriented market in order to keep pace with customer demand, where production was mainly focused on quantity. And consumers are not yet connected in technology the manufacturer or business groups therefore focus on producing the products that they want to produce in the market Then use the method to set policies for salespeople Try to sell the products that they produce (Cohen et al., 2006, p. 261) But when more competitors began along with the consumers it can be connected with each other by technology. Wider aspect of social communication and create a network that shares experiences gained from product consumption Businesses therefore have to switch to a customer focus strategy. With the main intention being Product improvement and sales promotion to meet the needs of the most customers.(Dennis & Kambil, 2003, p.45) As a result, marketers have to research customer needs. Then used to design and forward to the production process to get the product according to customer needs Which is loyalty to the brand This is called loyalty, both in an attitude and a behavior.(Kumar et al., 2008; Ryals, 2008, p. 323)

Objective

The purpose of this article is to synthesize the conceptual framework. These include various factors affecting brand management in product customization dimensions.

Expected benefits

In order to get a conceptual framework for promoting, implementing and developing brand values This will affect customer satisfaction leading to the development of brand value.

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Literature review

Mass Customization refers to the customization of a product / service. To meet customers or consumers who are different from person to person which affects the administrative structure and production of business to be flexible

enough to operate to obtain product / service features in both physical dimensions Perceive physical such as color, product appearance, size, taste, or emotional perception. The feeling of consumption, responsiveness to many different customers or consumers. Therefore it is difficult to manage as mentioned in the beginning Leading to the issue of applying this strategy Expanding from customized marketing to Massive customized marketing (Mass Customization) The word "Mass" or mass production Linked to the term "Customization", the custom or individual response (Salvador et al., 2009; McIntosh et al., 2010), "Mass Customization" is a combination of manufacturing-oriented concepts with Concept focused on customers By finding the core consumer demand (Core Attribute), the excess demand that is different (Option Attribute) and then managing to meet the needs of different customers for a large amount of income.

The importance of product customization can help consumers get the products that meet their needs. And as a result, consumers are loyal to the brand Business customization is part of the demonstration of brand value. Hence, it is a type of marketing strategy that is used in many businesses where customers can choose to receive services according to their needs (Customize). (Lusch, Vargo & O'Brien, 2006, p. 8)

Factors affecting the development of brand value in product customization according to customer needs. Many scholars have the opinion that to develop a successful brand value in product customization There are factors to consider: **Customer Coproducer** is a type of marketing strategy used by many businesses. Started to study in the year. 1980 by Toffler (1980) Toffler (1983);Gronroos(1990); Gummesson(19991); Davidow & Malone(1992); Pine (1993) Based on the concept that emphasizes the understanding of the needs of the internal customer From various dimensions that the customer wants per product In response to satisfaction And building ties This way of thinking is the source of the contemporary logic in doing business. In order to successfully manage matters, cooperation from the customer is required in the production chain. (Solveig Wikstrom, 1995, pp.6-19) Managing with this strategy will create value for your business both directly and indirectly in terms of revenue. And knowledge that is beneficial to the business at a low cost.

Components of customer engagement the use of customer relationship strategies, both to deliberately see results from consumption, barriers, usage problems Including the importance of improving the product to have a characteristic that responds to consumers. Classified as valuable knowledge to lead to sustainable business practice. This is an important function that marketers must contribute to making this happen. In this regard, the information needed from customers in terms of attitude and behavior are all influencing the adaptation of the entire business process. Can respond effectively Some businesses still implement this strategy. and success, build loyalty with customers (Wikstrom and Lundkvist, 1995)

Customer experience management refers to business ideas that can help a business be a customer-first organization. and deliver outstanding and personalized customer experiences. In today's digital world When a customer has multiple channels and touchpoints to access a product Delivering the first customer experience in every Interaction becomes even more important. By covering the whole physical experience and not physical, for example Brand awareness the presence of new discoveries in the product. Emphasizing the brand in a sense Customer brand loyalty (Randall, 2000) requires an element of the 3 aspects of the brand image are the symbolic image. Image of use and emotional image the perception can be either positive or negative. This is because the image of the product is managed by the business owner. (Verhoef et al., 2009) Having a positive image will benefit the product owner. When so Thus a marketing concept called Customer experience management, which is the process of converting the business strategy of managing the relevant customer experience with the product in order to benefit the business in fostering relationships. To lead product loyalty (Schmitt, 2010, p24) section.frow and Payne(2007) Experts use technology to explain that businesses need to have the ability to understand customer needs by creating products. That exceeds expectations until the customer becomes 'Brand advocacy', which is the goal. Gentile et al.(2007)

The importance of managing the customer experience from historical research data on the issue of marketing management, it was found that the topic of customer experience management. A study of 362 companies doing business in the United States was studied. (Rajgopal, 2000)80% believe companies can manage to deliver a "Superior experiencd" experience for their clients that influence their persistence. Customer experience from being involved in the use of marketing strategies. To make products with different attributes to meet the needs of customers. Until the effect on both physical perception and the emotional way of consumers (Gentile et al., 2007)

Collaborative Management The definition of managing cooperation with customers. (Collaborative Management) Collaborative management with customers. It is developed by taking the concept that is customer oriented (Customer

Oriented) by wanting to meet the needs of customers up to the internal level (Customer Insight). Customer Coproducer) In the past, customer coproducer was considered passive management (Solveig Wikstrom, 1995, p. 14-15) because when the product owner was introduced, it was proactive. It will be developed or designed according to the customer suggestions. But nowadays, cooperation management with customers Collaborative Management) It is the duty of the marketer to support and promote through all forms of communication including the use of computer technology so that customers can help in designing products that meet their needs. With customers It is therefore something that has been used to solve the problem of customer needs in many organizations. To meet customer satisfaction in products / services by Agranoff & McGuire (2003, p. 4) It has been defined that collaborative management is defined as "building a relationship between the company that owns the product and the customer with the aim of obtaining a message that expresses the need for product design to meet the needs of the customer. Will lead to a feeling of satisfaction in the product / service Later when it receives the desired updates Looking at this issue in a marketing strategy by Thomson & Perry (2006) Has given meaning that the management of cooperation with the customer is Marketing strategies used in response to the main customers or target groups.

The importance of managing a partnership with clients is to balance the investment of the business and the needs of the customer. The importance of management factors in cooperation with customers. Studying the importance of customer collaboration, Schierholz, Kolbe & Brenner (2007) scholars have discussed the importance of customer collaboration: Balancing corporate investments and customer needs There is something important

1. To increase the sales of products and services of the company continuously for a period of time.

2. To create a positive attitude towards products or services and the company makes customers know how to use the products Can properly remember And have a good image for the company and its products or services in Long term

3. To make customers loyal to a brand or service. If the company has products for sale

Multiple product lines Customers purchasing the Company's products in a particular product line are impressed by on the positive side, there will be a large chance that the company will be able to successfully cross-selecting products for sale.

4. To allow customers to recommend products or services to others. The word-of-mouth was born. (Words-of-Mouth) positively about a product which is more credible than the advertised claim.

From the concept of the customer cooperation management to be successful, it is important to

There is a mix of business strategies. Coordination from both the main line and the support line Including the use of technology and information systems Information in driving possible it to complete the operation fruition (Mohammed & Rashid, 2012)

Presenting products via online channels Along with the storefront that opens a regular sale Bringing the two together through activities to help facilitate the physical store. Merging online and offline marketing is a mix of styles and channels for customers to express their opinions. Open an opinion channel (Kotler, Kartajaya & Setiawan, 2017, p.49-76) Because advertising is no longer the last answer for consumers today. In addition, the opinions received from customers / consumers in various dimensions that arise will also help to develop and improve the brand and product to be satisfied with customers / consumers. With this principle, it becomes a marketing tool in business operations. To achieve the sales and profits that the organization wants. Responding to the needs of customers or target groups by looking at what the customer needs Then responding to customer needs By creating value by communicating back to customers In order to make customers satisfied And there was a need to buy Or is it offering a good experience? And obtaining new value, even if it is the same type of product but it offers more than just a simple product offering to customers.

Brand Equity has been described in a variety of academic works, for example, Schiffman & Kanuk (2007) said that brand value refers to the value inherent in a brand that consumers accept in meeting their needs. Quality "Customer Based Brand Equity", the brand value is what happens in the mind of the customer. Brand value is what happens in the minds of customers. Due to the fact that the target customers have knowledge and understanding Therefore, the brand value is a reflection of the effectiveness of a business' brand marketing operation. In that the customer experiences the feelings of that brand. Different levels of perception Affect different types of responses, which can be both positive and negative. Recognition of positive values shows affection. And a positive attitude towards products Build likes and lead to loyal customers. In the case of a positive brand value, it is an economic benefit both at the micro and macro levels. (Micro) (Kotler & Keller (2012) This is backed by historical Bovee, Houston & Thill (1995) research that says if a customer has a positive perception of brand value, it is an intangible asset of that business (Aaker, 1996).

Brand Values From an enterprise perspective, Farquhar (1989) states that brand value is It is added value to the company, store or consumer. This is the relationship between branding and customer behavior that affects the sales of products of various companies or organizations. Brand value can be measured through increased cash flow with the presence of all branded products. As a result of pricing that is higher than competitors. (Premium Pricing Cost reduction in marketing promotion activities and an increase in market share (Incremental Cash Flow) target in adding value to that brand There will be two main reasons so that the business can set a price for the brand if trading occurs. To add intangible assets to the balance sheet. In addition, brand value is beneficial to the business of producing and distributing new products. and help in brand management for flexibility If an entity is in a crisis, it also acts as a protection against new competitors entering the market (Kotler, 2003)

Brand value from a merchant perspective Brand value can be measured by the brand leveraging of a competitor's brand (Aaker, 1991), meaning a strong brand is recognized by merchants. Distributor and extensive distribution of that brand Will make consumers know Familiar with that brand as well as a result, it has the power to negotiate with customers and distributors. As well as being allocated a good space to place products in the shop of the dealer or distributor Brand value from a consumer perspective, Keller (1998) defines the term "brand value". Brand value in the minds of consumers That is the result of knowledge about the brand (Brand Knowledge) of consumers who respond to the marketing activities (Marketing Response) of the brand, which will be different. The brand value from the consumer perspective is a result of the consumer's positive attitude towards the brand. Attitude is defined as a connection between something that is relevant, related to a brand, in which the consumer evaluates the stimulus in his / her memory. Therefore, the measurement of brand value must be measured from the consumer's attitude towards the brand, which is an important factor affecting consumer purchasing behavior. The added value of the brand will increase the confidence in making purchasing decisions. Increase the level of satisfaction in using the product It also makes it easier to process a large amount of information about a consumer's product.

Importance of Brand Value Farquhar (1989) has stated that brand value is It is added value to the company, store or consumer. This is the relationship between branding and customer behavior that affects the sales of products of various companies or organizations. Brand value can be measured through increased cash flow with the presence of all branded products. This is the result of setting a price higher than its competitors. (Premium Pricing) Cost reduction in marketing promotion activities and the increase in market share (Incremental Cash Flow) goal of adding value to the brand. There are two main reasons for this: to allow businesses to set a price for the brand if a deal occurs. To add intangible assets to the balance sheet. In addition, brand value is beneficial to the business of producing and distributing new products. And help in brand management for flexibility If the company is in crisis, it also acts as a protection against new competitors entering the market (Kotler, 2012). Adopting the concept of brand value It will deliver results and products that can create brand value that stimulates customer awareness of decision making and brand value perception. The important thing is Emphasis on quality, product manufacturing standards and the matter of excellent service There is continuous product improvement to be up to date. (Johnston, Robert & Kong, Xiangyu, 2011)

II. The conceptual framework gained from the study

From the sequence of steps, the relationship of elements that affect the development of brand value. As shown in the order above Able to synthesize results as a conceptual framework Developing product brand value in response to customer satisfaction Participation in building And customer experience management, as shown in Figure 1.

Brand management in product customization dimensions participation in building and customer experience management.

Figure 1: Concept of brand management in product customization, participation in the creation and management of the customer experience.

Source: from literature review Related theories and synthesis as a conceptual framework

From the conceptual framework of brand management in product customization dimensions, participation in building and customer experience management above. This shows that the factors that are important to product customization. For the development of brand value, products include customer satisfaction. Therefore, businesses should take into account the aforementioned factors. To be able to focus on the development of brand value

III. Sum up

Bringing the conceptual framework to develop the brand value of the product to happen It must contain important factors: Customer Coproducer, Customer Experience management, Collaborative Management In terms of support by product customization Another important issue that marketers must pay attention to is development success. Especially if the product cannot show its identity. Making the product not much different Competitive advantages can therefore make a difference in the perception of consumers. For the reason that there are many competitors and the ability of manufacturing technology results in the appearance of physical products to be similar or identical (Epstein, 2007; Varian, 2006) Thus making a physical difference (Product Differentiable) To the product is difficult to do The fact that products can be easily imitated This makes creating an identity and intangible difference a problem. Therefore, the approach developed later is Emotional creation of product identity for customers such as Perceived Value, Brand Awareness and Brand Recognition (Fader & Hardie, 2007; Epstein & Yuthas, 2007) in order for customers / consumers to keep these things in mind, which becomes that brand-buying behavior

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